

Ecology and the politics of survival

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Our planet is unique. It is the only one we know which contains life, and it is this fact of life which is, to man, the most important fact about the earth. Therefore, his most important question is whether life will continue here. It is simply a question of survival.

Conservationists sometimes forget this, and they argue about secondary things. The basic issue of life and death is often not raised when they discuss, say, pollution. All energies are focused on identifying the pollutants and polluters in a scientific witch hunt, with the solution of each pollution crisis being sought in the same technology that spawned it. Criticisms, and solutions, are narrowed to treat limited aspects of society, while the basic flaws are ignored. No effort is concentrated on our lifestyle that has created and requires these environmental crimes. This whole lifestyle is hitched to an unlimited, infinite growth economy which cannot survive in a limited, finite environment for very long.

We, as conservationists, have looked superficially at the problems of the environment and seen only the symptoms of a deeper malaise. We have seized on pollution and the extinction of species and a handful of other crises and let pass the fundamental ordering of our society. We have also turned to aspects of this way of life to solve our problems. Traditional economic criteria have justified wildlife areas and traditional political processes have been used to set aside these areas. These are the methods of a society that cannot live within its environment, and they are inappropriate when we are rapidly destroying that environment.

When these peripheral issues are shed, the central issue is clear – survival. It is also clear that survival is a problem of the inter-relationships between organisms and their environment. It is an ecological problem and ecology provides the only rationale for environmental action. Ecological insight has become of critical survival value to mankind and this insight suggests that our present way of life has a negative survival value. Man relates to an imaginary environment of infinite resources while the real environment is one of limited resources. He is undergoing an exponential expansion while the real ecosystem is in a dynamic equilibrium.

The question of survival is meaningful in ecological terms and so the cures to our ecological insanity must be found in such terms. Individuals and communities must begin to accept the ecological realities of this earth. We must accept, as real, the limitations of our environment and reject economic systems which say otherwise; we must accept, as necessary and vital, the complexity of our ecosystem and reject attempts to simplify it; and we must accept, as essential, the regulation of all organisms within the carrying capacity of this ecosystem and reject, as unecological, those philosophies that advocate continuous, mindless, growth. These are answers to a bigger question than conservationists have yet tackled. They embrace all the problems that have been attacked hitherto but give to them all a basic unity.

These answers require action. Individual commitment to the ecological ethic is needed along with an articulate dialogue with all members of the human community. It is vital that an

awareness of the environment and life's utter dependence on it are disseminated as widely as possible. Environmentalists must act to prevent further deterioration of the biosphere. We also need to explore basic alternatives to our lifestyle so we can show the community that man can live within its environment.

All these actions involve changing the minds and goals of men. They are, in this sense, political; but this is not the politics of compromise – the art of the possible. Environmentalists should use political processes because they are convenient tools whose functions are understood by society. Our politics must be secondary, however intimately related to the real issues of life and death.

Therefore the tasks before us if we are to survive are:

- making the community and its political leaders aware of the crisis and that it affects them
- undertaking efforts to stop or at least delay the wild growth of the earth's human population with its deleterious effects on our resources
- discovering basic alternatives to our present style which will be more in harmony with all other forms of life and our shared environment.

There is not time to find another planet capable of supporting life, so all our attention must be directed to keeping this one habitable to ensure the survival of ourselves, our society, and all living things.

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